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REENGINEERING OF BUSINESS PROCESSES OF THE PROVISION OF PUBLIC SERVICES

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Abstract. The authors identify the specifics of reengineering of business processes of the provision of public services, as well as to study of the problems and prospects of these processes' realization. The authors note that the reasons for carrying out of reengineering of business processes of state bodies can be the following: change of state functions of a state body; emergence of new types of public services or replacement of old types with new ones. The authors think that the expediency of transferring state authority to another body of executive power at the horizontal level of state administration is also established on the basis of a comprehensive analysis of the sphere of state regulation. Finally, the decision to change the procedure for providing a state service is made in the case of establishing the need to maintain state regulation of established relations, but using other mechanisms.

Keywords: business processes, reengineering, public services, state bodies, state authorities.

Introduction. The methodology of reengineering of business processes can be applied both to the activities of the state structure in general and to individual processes.

A key measure to achieve goals within the perspective of internal processes is the automation of processes that are designed for the first time, which in turn will allow to relieve the employees involved in certain processes and to increase the efficiency of their activities, as well as to reduce the time required to perform this or that another function.

Thus, the achievement of goals within the perspective of internal processes is directly related to ensuring the overall economic efficiency of the state structure and its financing, which is focused on results, not on costs.

Literature review

The authors of the article (Fetais, Aljazzi, Galal M. Abdella, Khalifa N. Al-Khalifa & Abdel Magid Hamouda, 2022) believe that business process reengineering is an approach to improve the efficiency of an organization. It was developed mainly in the private sector to maintain a successful business model despite growing global competition. Business process reengineering represents a fundamental improvement in the core organizational structure. This article examines recent researches on business process reengineering and identifies the success factors of business process reengineering projects and their relationship to the human-technology-organization system. The aim of the study is to identify the success factors and challenges of business processes reengineering. In conclusion, the article focuses on the factors that will help to implement reengineering of business processes with wider use in various sectors.

The purpose of the article (Peter O'Neill & Amrik S. Sohal, 1999) is to help to demystify confusion in business process reengineering. This is achieved through a literature review covering the period from the late 1980s to 1998. The review

included articles published in leading business journals as well as books published on the subject. First, the document discusses the need for reengineering, and then discusses the literature under the following headings: definition of business process reengineering, tools and methods of business processes reengineering, coexistence of business process reengineering and TQM, understanding of organizational processes, reengineering problem and organizational reengineering using business process reengineering. The review shows that there is considerable confusion as to what exactly is business process reengineering. The authors pay special attention to defining the reengineering of business processes.

The authors of the article (Bhaskar, H. L. & Singh, R. P., 2014) believe that business process reengineering is a tool to help organizations to improve quality, customer service, reduce operating costs and become leaders in their field. Business process reengineering can act as an important strategic tool to ensure a sustainable competitive advantage for foreign or Indian manufacturing companies (public and private ones) in the current context. This study was carried out in order to collect and review the work done so far in the field of business process reengineering and quality management. The focus of this study was to provide a comprehensive overview of the overall development of the concept, theories, approaches, challenges and outcomes of business processes reengineering. The conclusion was based on previous studies, and it was concluded that the application of business process reengineering in India's manufacturing sector is not difficult.

The authors (Al-Anqoudi, Younis, Abdullah Al-Hamdani, Mohamed Al-Badawi & Rachid Hedjam, 2021) argue that the value of re-engineering business of processes in improving business is undoubted. Still, it's incredibly complex, time-consuming and expensive. The purpose of this study is to review the available literature on the use of machine learning for business process reengineering. The review examines the available literature on the fundamentals of business process

reengineering, methodologies, tools, methods and applications of machine learning to automate business process reengineering. The study covers more than 200 research papers published between 2015 and 2020 on reputable scientific publication platforms: Scopus, Emerald, Science Direct, IEEE and the British Library. The results show that business process reengineering is a well-established area with science-based frameworks, methodologies, tools and methods that support decision-making by generating and analyzing relevant data.

In view of the above relevance of the topic of this study, the purpose of the article is to identify the specifics of reengineering of business processes of the provision of public services, as well as to study of the problems and prospects of these processes' realization.

Methodology

In general, reining in business processes is considered one of the main methods of modernizing public services. Business process re-engineering refers to a management strategy aimed at analyzing and designing the work processes of an organization that aims to facilitate organizations in a fundamental rethink of how activities are conducted to improve customer service in the provision of public services; reducing operating costs and avoiding risks associated with the process.

The re-engineering of business processes of the state body is a fundamental rethink and radical redesign of business processes to achieve the sharp, download-like performance indicators (KPIs) of the state body on the implementation of public services, such as cost, quality, availability, and performance.

Main part

If we consider the reengineering of business processes of the state structure in more detail, the following should first be noted.

Reengineering of business processes of the state body is a fundamental rethinking and radical redesign of business processes to achieve dramatic, leap-like

improvements in the performance indicators of a state body in the context of the provision of public services, such as cost, quality, availability, delivery time and labor costs.

The reasons for carrying out of reengineering of business processes of state bodies can be the following:

- change of state functions of a state body;
- emergence of new types of public services or replacement of old types with new ones [2; 7].

The single methodology for reengineering of the processes of providing of public services and optimizing control and supervision and permitting activities is currently not fixed in regulatory and methodological documents.

Reengineering of public services is an activity aimed at radical restructuring of the current practice of their provision. According to the degree of influence on the organizational structure of state bodies, evolutionary and revolutionary reengineering of business processes are distinguished [3; 8].

In particular, with an evolutionary approach to reengineering, the internal integration of various business processes is optimized, but no significant changes are made in the functioning of state bodies. With a revolutionary approach to reengineering, all business processes are redesigned, and the state body is reoriented to new types of public service provision.

At the current stage, the following types of reengineering of public services are distinguished (Figure 1) [4; 8].

Figure 1. Types of reengineering of public services

In particular, the decision to liquidate a state service may be made due to its actual lack of demand, as well as its duplication. The fact that a state service is not in demand is established on the basis of departmental statistics based on the number of applications from applicants. In the case of detection of low or zero values for the specified indicator for several years, it is advisable to initiate consideration of the issue of making changes to normative legal acts in terms of the cancellation of the relevant state authority or its transfer to the market. Duplication of the service is established on the basis of the analysis of regulatory and legal acts. The discovery of the fact of granting two or more state bodies (including subordinate organizations) with the same state authority should be the basis for applying the specified measure of reengineering [4; 9].

The decision to transfer state authority to another level of public legal entities can be made on the basis of a comprehensive analysis of all possible sources of information about the state service and its interdependent powers, both of a normative and practical nature. The main decision-making criteria should be the following:

- the availability of a reserve of resources for the proper provision of a state service (performance of a state function);
- determination of the limits of possible risks from improper execution of authority (for the state as a whole and at the level of regions);
- the presence of an obvious potential for improving the quality of public service provision from the applicant's point of view;
- the availability of a practical possibility to monitor and control the quality of the implementation of delegated powers without significant expenditure of resources [1; 5].

The expediency of transferring state authority to another body of executive power at the horizontal level of state administration is also established on the basis of a comprehensive analysis of the sphere of state regulation. Mandatory conditions for the transfer of state authority from one state body to another should be the conformity of objects of regulation, spheres of management with the transferred authority and reduction of state costs for the implementation of state authority.

The decision to change the procedure for providing a state service is made in the case of establishing the need to maintain state regulation of established relations, but using other mechanisms. In particular, the object of state regulation or the mechanism by which it is implemented may be changed.

Among the most important factors influencing business processes for the provision of public services, it is necessary to highlight the following (Figure 2) [2; 5].

Figure 2. Factors affecting business processes for the provision of public services

The criterion for the application of the measure to establish a "new" state authority is to identify the fact of providing a state service, performing a state function in the absence of a legal basis for its provision (performance). In such a case, it is necessary to make changes to the legislative and sub-legislative legal acts for the purposes of normative consolidation of the authority that is actually performed. In addition, the decision to establish a state authority can be made upon the fact of identifying the inadequacy of state regulation if there is an existing need for it [3; 4].

Conclusions

In general, the reengineering of business processes of the provision of public services includes the following stages:

- project development and separation of business processes of the state body: the goals and objectives of the reengineering project are determined, the reengineering team is formed;
- documentation of business processes of the state body: construction of graphic models of business processes is carried out, complex operations of business processes are timed;
- comparative analysis of business processes (benchmarking): development of the image of the future state body and state services is provided, as well as the system of views on the new state body in accordance with its goals and capabilities;
- analysis of problems and redesign of business processes to identify difficult places in technological and business processes;
- introduction of new business processes, technologies, as well as evaluation of results based on the efficiency of functioning of business processes with the criteria set at the beginning of reengineering, taking into account costs by types of functional activity.

In fact, state regulation of innovative advertising can be attributed to the business processes of state bodies.

Discussion

Since business process reengineering is considered consistent and continuous process, it is necessary to introduce a management cycle, and there should be a continuous process of revision of the service itself, its production and provision.

After the previous business process reengineering steps are implemented, their effects are tracked and evaluated, new ideas must be considered and put forward for a new business process reengineering cycle. In addition, recommendations should also be reviewed for their systemic applicability, i.e. when an evaluation of an individual service offers a recommendation that can be used to improve other services, this

capability should be used immediately rather than waiting for a symmetrical recommendation on other services.

Once the evaluation recommendations have been received, it is advisable to develop a register of recommendations or a plan for their implementation. Implementation Plan – is a document that sets out recommendations and defines changing the resources, success rates and timelines available or allocated to responsible agencies or departments to implement recommendations. This plan must be followed separately, otherwise it can connect to a new Business Process Reengineering Monitoring Cycle.

References

1. AbdEllatif, M.; Farhan, M.S.; Shehata, N.S. Overcoming business process reengineering obstacles using ontology-based knowledge map methodology. *Futur. Comput. Informatics J.* 2018, 3, 7–28.
2. Al-Anqoudi, Younis, Abdullah Al-Hamdani, Mohamed Al-Badawi, and Rachid Hedjam. 2021. "Using Machine Learning in Business Process Re-Engineering" *Big Data and Cognitive Computing* 5, no. 4: 61. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bdcc5040061>.
3. Asikhia, U.O.; Awolusi, D.O. Assessment of critical success factors of business process re-engineering in the Nigerian oil and gas industry. *S. Afr. J. Bus. Manag.* 2015, 46, 1–14.
4. Bhaskar, H. L., and Singh, R. P. (2014). Business process reengineering: a recent review. *Global Journal of Business Management*, 8(2), 24-51.
5. Brandon, B.; Guimaraes, T. Increasing Bank BPR Benefits by Managing Project Phases. *Knowl. Process Manag.* 2016, 23, 136–146.

6. Fetais, Aljazzi, Galal M. Abdella, Khalifa N. Al-Khalifa, and Abdel Magid Hamouda. 2022. "Business Process Re-Engineering: A Literature Review-Based Analysis of Implementation Measures" *Information* 13, no. 4: 185. <https://doi.org/10.3390/info13040185>.
7. Marquez-Chamorro, A.E.; Resinas, M.; Ruiz-Cortes, A. Predictive Monitoring of Business Processes: A Survey. *IEEE Trans. Serv. Comput.* 2017, 11, 962–977.
8. Park, K.O. The Relationship between BPR Strategy and Change Management for the Sustainable Implementation of ERP: An Information Orientation Perspective. *Sustainability* 2018, 10, 3080.
9. Peter O'Neill, Amrik S. Sohal, Business Process Reengineering A review of recent literature, *Technovation*, Volume 19, Issue 9, 1999, Pages 571-581, ISSN 0166-4972, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-4972\(99\)00059-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-4972(99)00059-0).
10. Tax, N.; Verenich, I.; la Rosa, M.; Dumas, M. Predictive business process monitoring with LSTM neural networks. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Advanced Information Systems Engineering*, Essen, Germany, 12–16 June 2017; Springer: New York, NY, USA, 2017.